

Port of Piraeus (EL)

This fiche includes maps displaying the location of the sampling points (SPOs) around the port of Piraeus (EL) with measurements of NO₂ and PM_{2.5} in 2023 (E1a validated data AQ e-Reporting). The tables include additional information on the annual mean concentrations of each SPO with available data (data coverage larger than 75%), distances of the SPOs from the port area, location of the SPO in one of the 8 wind sectors around the port (WS: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW), population living in the WS within 10 km from the port, and trends of annual mean concentrations (2005-2023) when available. This information has been complemented with the EEA air quality annual maps (1 km x 1 km), covering the whole area around the port and showing in the boxplot the different levels concentrations over the port area compared to the surrounding region, including the weighted area means for the different land cover classes.

The presented information is based only on SPOs reported to the EEA, additional SPOs or data may exist at national level.

Port of Piraeus (EL)

Port area and NO₂ air quality SPOs around the port within 5 and 10 km

Port area and PM_{2.5} air quality SPOs around the port within 5, 10 and 20 km

Pozzoli, L., Gressent, A., Soares, J., Colette, A., Monge, S. & González Ortiz, A. (2025). Air quality around ports (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2024/12, version 2, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17416089>).
[ETC HE Report 2024/12: Air quality around ports — Eionet Portal](#)

NO₂ SPOs in 2023 around the port

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Greece	GR0030A	Traffic	37.94	23.65	57.61		0.00	E	474,118
Greece	GR0029A	Industrial	37.98	23.71	15.36		6.58	E	474,118

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European Environment Agency
European Topic Centre
Human health and the environment

PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the port

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Greece	GR0030A	Traffic	37.94	23.65	13.10		0.00	E	474,118
Greece	GR0038A	Industrial	38.05	23.54	16.38		7.82	NW	21,377
Greece	GR0003A	Traffic	37.99	23.73	18.91		8.47	E	474,118
Greece	GR0039A	Background	38.00	23.82	11.43		16.15	E	474,118

Annual mean NO₂ concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the port area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

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Annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the port area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

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